

Bio-floc based tilapia farming

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Introduction

Aquaculture, being a youngest and fastest-growing food production venture in recent years, is supplying world's cheapest protein source, but on the other side, many lingering questions have been raised about how long this rapid expansion can be sustained (FAO, 2020). This is because, initially, aquaculture has been practiced as monoculture, which demands large quantity of water, large amount of fishmeal for feed preparation and vast amount of land areas to achieve high production (Boyd et al., 2020). In addition to this, improper disposal of aquaculture waste to the environment has created many negative consequences such as soil and water contamination, pathogen transmission and eutrophication of water bodies. These environmental issues were seriously damaged the long-term viability of aquaculture's industry (Verdegem, 2013). Recently, biofloc-based systems have been proposed and disseminated among the progressive farmers to solve these problems and to ensure the long-term sustainability of this sector (Bossier and Ekasari, 2017).

The biofloc technique (BFT) was initially developed for shrimp farming industry to address the problem of disease outbreaks (Treece, 2019). BFT has now been successfully adopted for many commercial fin fish rearing practices, especially in tilapia culture (*Oreochromis sp.*) (Emerenciano

et al., 2021). Tilapia is one of the world's most widely produced fish species and cultured around more than 114 countries (FAO, 2020). The main concept of BFT is to prevent the accumulation of toxic nitrogen levels in fish tanks through the growth of specific microorganisms which converts this waste into edible protein for fish. BFT is typically performed in a closed system with minimal water exchange, without much complicated filters and minimal discharge of nutrients. The conversion of nitrogen into microbial biomass is accomplished by increased supply of oxygen to the water through aeration and adjusting the water's carbon: nitrogen (C: N) ratio through the supplementation of carbon sources. The added advantages like minimal water usage with better maintenance of water quality, recycling of nutrients with *in-situ* food production and minimizing the disease outbreaks with better immunity of animals making this system as the need of the hour for aquaculture industry.

Tilapia culture in biofloc technology (BFT)

BFT systems are widely used in shrimp farming around the world. However, the success in shrimp farming slowly attracted the fish farmers to adopt this system for better production. Among the various farmed finfishes, tilapia is an excellent choice for BFT based production systems as it is an omnivore-filter feeder. Additionally, it can grow and survive well in dense systems like biofloc system.

In biofloc system, bacteria develop fast and attached to many other organisms and organic particles, forming bio flocs particle sizes ranging from 0.1 to a few mm, which can be quickly

harvested and assimilated by tilapia. Tilapia grown in BFT ponds were compared to tilapia reared in appropriate control ponds, and it was clear that the control ponds' fish had been starving and rushed desperately to the feed granules applied twice a day. In contrast, tilapia grown in BFT ponds ate quietly, indicating that they were not starved before feeding. Smaller fish that struggle to compete with larger fish in regular ponds should benefit from the semi-continuous feeding provided by the bio floc, resulting in better uniform growth of tilapia in BFT ponds.

Tank set-up, biofloc preparation and seed stocking

Biofloc based tilapia can be reared in lined ponds, indoor tanks, concrete tanks and HDPE circular tanks with central drainage system for better maintenance of water quality. Most preferred type of biofloc tank is indoor based circular tanks made up of HDPE sheets (above 540 GSM thickness). In general, 4 m dia circular tanks supported with stainless steel frame and GI poles were used. Initially, bottom is designed with concrete and brick-stone and then it will be provided with central drainage system. For this, either a slope is provided towards the central part of tank or a standing PVC pipe, with holes, is used. Followed by this, outer structures like frame, supporting poles and aeration facilities were provided. Then, HDPE sheets will be laid over this frame. Maximum care should be given while spreading this HDPE sheet.

For biofloc preparation, there are many methods have been adopted by farmers. In the initial days, heterotrophic bacteria were developed using pond soil, with the help organic carbon and vigorous aeration. However, the introduction of various commercial probiotics and efficient microbial products opened the gateway for other viable biofloc production methods. The following table predict the ingredients used in commercial biofloc production by progressive farmers;

Using probiotics (for 10000 L)		Using EM solution (10000 L)	
Salt	10 Kg	Salt	10 Kg
Calcium carbonate	0.5 Kg	Rice bran	1 Kg
Molasses	1 Kg	Jaggery	1 Kg
Probiotics	250 – 300 g	EM solution	1 L

After preparing this initial solution, it will be kept for 2-3 days for floc formation. Once floc is formed, it will be mixed with tank water. After 7-10 days, once biofloc is reached a volume of 20-25 ml/l in Imhoff cone, tilapia can be stocked in biofloc tanks.

Mono-sex tilapia seed purchased from the certified hatcheries can be stocked in biofloc systems. The recommended stocking density is 200-300 seed/m³ to obtain a production of 20-25 tones/ha.

Feeding of tilapia in bio floc

The proper C/N ratio (10:1 to 15:1) can be achieved through adequate feeding, promoting ammonium uptake from the water. In order to save money, an appropriate strategy of feed that incorporates recycled microbial protein is also required. Feed rations in biofloc based tilapia production systems can be lower than the conventional ponds. In general, feeding pellets with low protein percentage can maintain the recommended C:N ratio or supplement the feed pellets with carbonaceous material (cassava, wheat or other flour, molasses, etc.) to maintain the C:N ratio.

Maintenance of floc in culture system

BFT tilapia culture has a high respiration rate due to the dense fish biomass and the microbial community that metabolizes the organic residues. Therefore, continuous supply of oxygen (> 6mg/l) is essential in biofloc systems. This can be achieved through various aeration systems available in the market, however while selecting the aerator, size of the fish and the biomass of the tank should be taken into account. In addition to oxygen, water ammonia level needs to be checked daily to maintain the C:N ration of 10:1 to 15:1. Based on the level of floc, measured in the Imhoff cone, supplementation of carbon source is recommended.

Intensive tilapia BFT ponds are typically small, ranging from 100 to 1000 m², due to the difficulty in mixing a large water body. This type of ponds was also provided with a central drain, in the middle of pond with a standpipe and valve. The drain is usually opened twice in a day, allowing the dark sludge to drain out until clear pond water emerges.

Conclusion

The contemporary challenges faced by tilapia industry could be well addressed by this sustainable production system. Further the feed recycling and reduced water exchange greatly enhance the cost-effectiveness of tilapia production. However, before shifting from traditional fish farming practice to this modern production system, farmer should get at least technical knowledge and minimum field level experience to this system for tasting the success in biofloc system. Government and other policy makers should keep this in mind and work towards the sustainable production of tilapia in the future.

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